

The Plant Review

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A heavenly honeysuckle:
Growing *Lonicera calcarata*

Pennies from heaven:
The virtues of *Lunaria*

Avens be praised:
What's new with geums

In praise of *Paeonia peregrina*

Nora De Angelli discusses the cultural connections of a Romanian native of rare beauty

A BEAUTIFUL FOLK LEGEND explains the appearance of red peonies in many regions of Romania. It is said that a long time ago, in a forest near a kingdom, lived some beautiful fairies who could not stand the shallowness of mortals, and would turn into a monster any person who dared to trespass on their realm.

People were scared by these stories and, following the advice of their king, stayed far away from the cursed land. However, Peony, the king's young son, who had an adventurous spirit, heard about the fairies and, when he reached adolescence, ventured to the forbidden lands to find for himself the malefic fairies.

As soon as he reached the forest he fell into a deep sleep and the curse of the fairies rained down upon him. However, captivated by his beauty, they chose to transform him not into a monster but a flower, the most beautiful in the kingdom. As the peony blooms, just after sunset, and the dew settles on the beautifully coloured, fragrant flowers, the drops of water are said to be the tears of the young Peony, eternally grieving with regret for disobeying his father's commands (Chivu 2022). It is a fittingly romantic story for a flower that was, on 27 September 2022, formally declared the National Flower of Romania.

A legend tells of a Romanian prince who was transformed into *Paeonia peregrina*.

In nature

There are five species of *Paeonia* that are native to Romania, from Banat to Dobrogea and from Oltenia to Transylvania, all of great horticultural potential. It is perhaps the most beautiful of all of these, *P. peregrina*, that is the subject of this article.

Paeonia peregrina is a Balkan species, occurring from Italy to Turkey and Moldova, and found in Romania on the Dobrogea Plateau in the east of the country (Chifu *et al.* 2014). It is a xerophytic species, found in stony, arid, rocky areas, at the edge of forests or clearings, and less frequently in grasses. It usually grows in the shade of deciduous broad-leaved, pine or mixed forests. It prefers calcareous substrates, at altitudes from 50 to 1,500m.

Reaching heights of 60–80cm, the stems bear deeply divided, two- to five-lobed, dark-green leaves. The solitary flowers, which are subtended by leaf-like, green bracts, are large, blood-red and strongly scented, with a perfume reminiscent of roses. The stamens are numerous, with yellow or red filaments.

The most distinct characters of *Paeonia peregrina* are its toothed leaf segments and dark-red, cup-shaped corollas which distinguish it from *P. officinalis* (Ciocârlan 2009). The scented flowers and the stamens, very rich in pollen, attract many pollinators such as common honeybees, *Apis mellifera*. Quite often, insects use the flowers as sleeping places, crowding inside the large corollas at dusk.

Paeonia peregrina is an endangered species (Oprea 2005), currently threatened by uncontrolled deforestation and the loss of habitat to arable land. It is sensitive to desertification due to climate change and is protected by law, featuring in the Red List of Higher Plants from Romania.

Cultural significance

Peonies are popular in Romania and, besides the indigenous taxa, three other species are commonly cultivated: *P. lactiflora*, *Paeonia officinalis* and *P. suffruticosa*, along with at least 130 cultivars of those species. As well as in gardens, peonies are also grown in large glasshouses and peony farms for cut-flower production.

In honour of the peony, now considered “an element of national identity”, 15 May was chosen as Romanian Peony Day. In spring each year, festivals and popular celebrations are organized

in several areas of the country, when the flowers are in full bloom. At these, people recite poems, tell stories or sing and dance to traditional folk songs related to peonies and peony legends, while dressed in traditional folk clothing adorned with vividly coloured peony motifs.

As a final tribute to the beauty and symbolic resonance of these plants, the Romanian Ministry of Defence recently adopted the red peony as the floral symbol of Veterans Day, celebrated on 11 November in honour of those Romanians who have fought and fallen in the conflicts of the past. ○

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